

MECHANICAL AND ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES OF MICRO/NANOCOMPOSITES VIA CNT DISPERSED RESIN FILM INFUSION PROCESS

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SUMMARY

Carbon nanotube (CNT) embedded B-stage resin films were prepared by two different dispersion methods: a homogenizer and a 3-roll mill. The contents of CNT were varied 3-10wt%. The resin film infusion (RFI) process has been applied in the fabrication of CNT/epoxy hybrid composites by stacking the carbon fabric and the CNT embedded resin film alternately. The morphology and electrical properties of composites were characterized. Experimental results confirmed that the electrical and mechanical properties are strongly dependent on the contents and the distribution of CNTs in the B-stage resin film.

Keywords: B-stage resin film, CNT, 3-roll mill, homogenizer, resin film infusion

INTRODUCTION

As an effective nanoscale filler, CNTs have attracted great interests in the field of electronic applications as well as structural applications [1, 2] due to their uniqueness in the mechanical, thermal, optical and electrical properties. Many investigations have been carried out on nanocomposite materials incorporated with CNTs. However, their potential as reinforcements for polymers has not been fully realized because their high aspect ratio caused severe entanglement. Furthermore, the chemically inert nature of CNTs leads to poor dispersion and interfacial interactions with polymer matrix [3]. High viscosity is one of significant problems in the processing of composites. If CNTs in the matrix are well distributed and dispersed, the content is severely limited within the range of ~2 wt%.

A variety of research efforts has been devoted to improving the dispersion of CNT, with respect to mechanical dispersion methods and surface modification of CNTs based on chemical methods [4]. Most of mechanical dispersion methods involve high shear mixing and ultrasonic energy. Recently, a 3-roll mill equipped with extraordinarily narrow gap setting has to achieve good dispersion of CNTs [5]. Practical merits of this processing technique compared to other techniques are producing large amount of

mixture with high rate, giving uniform shear to mixture through cylinder-type rolls and operating under the elevated viscous conditions.

In this work, we fabricated carbon fiber-reinforced polymer composites hybridized with CNTs via resin film infusion process. CNTs were incorporated into the polymer matrix with relatively high amount. We also compared the degree of CNT dispersion in matrix polymer processed by two mixing methods; a 3-roll mill and a homogenizer. The homogenizer was selected for comparison because of easy availability and very high rotation speed. Electrical property of hybrid composites with respect to CNT contents and dispersion methods was also investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

B-stage resin films including CNT (multi-walled CNT, Hanwha nanotech, CM-95) were prepared by mixing epoxy resin, YD-128 (Kukdo Chemistry, Korea), with curing agent, dicyandiamide (DICY, Kukdo Chemicals, Korea). As an accelerator, N-(dichlorophenyl)-N',Ndimethylurea (DCMU, Kukdo Chemicals) were used. Dimethyl formamide (DMF) and 2-Methoxy ethanol (MCS) (Sam-chun Chemical, Korea) were used as a solvent. Plain woven carbon fabrics (Mitsubishi, TR50 fiber, 3k) were used for composites.

Preparation of B-stage resin film

Epoxy resin mixtures with CNTs were prepared by two different dispersion methods: a homogenizer and a 3-roll mill (80E, EXAKT). In case of the homogenizer, all ingredients were added into a beaker and then agitated with a rotation speed of 3000 rpm at 25°C for 20 min. The other resin mixture was processed by a 3-roll mill operated at 250 rpm (Figure 1). Roll gap setting was kept below 1 μm by force mode during the operation. The resin/CNTs mixture was processed repeatedly more than 5 times.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of 3-roll mill process.

Resin films were fabricated using CNT-dispersed resin mixture. As shown in Figure 2, the film was casted by a knife of 200~300 μm thickness followed by B-stage curing at 120°C for 10min.

Figure 2. Fabrication of resin film by a casting knife.

Composite sample fabrication

Using B-stage resin films, hybrid composites were fabricated by autoclave process. First, B-stage resin films (size: 80mm×80mm) were stacked between carbon fabrics (size: 80mm×80mm). Resin was infiltrated into the carbon fabric under the mild thermal and pressure condition (80°C and 74psi) for 1hr and then composites were cured at 120 °C and 74psi for 2hr 30min.

Characterization

Surface of B-stage resin film and degree of CNT dispersion were observed by digital camera (Powershot G3, Canon, Japan) and scanning electron microscope (SEM, JEOL-5800, Japan) respectively. Electrical conductivities of hybrid composites were measured for 15mm×15mm specimens using a Keithley 2100 multimeter in both the in-plane and the out-of-plane directions. Electrical conductivity of composites was calculated by following equations:

$$\sigma = 1/\rho \quad (1)$$

$$\rho = RA/\ell \quad (2)$$

(R: resistance, A: area, ℓ : length, σ : electrical conductivity)

Surface conductivity of resin films containing CNTs was measured by 4-probe method for 50mm×50mm film specimens using MCP-T610. In order to examine the effect of CNTs on mechanical property, a short beam shear test (ASTM D2344) was carried out.

RESULTS

Pass time for optimal distribution of CNTs

As discussed above, we proposed a 3-roll mill process in order to distribute or disperse large amount of CNTs into the epoxy mixture effectively. However, there are still inevitable limitations due to the problem of process itself. During the processing, the mixture has been changed to semi-dried slurry and it was impossible to process mixture of simple epoxy with CNT due to the high viscosity. To solve this problem, we added solvents such as Dimethyl formamide (DMF) and 2-Methoxy ethanol (MCS) which were able to lower the viscosity of CNT/epoxy dramatically. These solvents were volatilized from the surface of thin resin film and actually removed after B-stage curing. The other issue was how many times the mixture should be passed through to distribute CNTs uniformly. The pass time has a significant effect on the degree of CNT distribution and the processing time. Since it takes a long time to process under the gap distance of 1 μm , the optimal pass time should be determined. We examined the surface conductivity of resin films of CNT (3wt%)/epoxy mixture processed by a 3-roll mill. This CNT/epoxy mixture was sampled with the pass times of 1, 3, 5, 7 and 10. All samples were casted to 200 μm films. Figure 3 shows the conductivity of resin films. It is noted that the electrical conductivity with increased pass time conversed up to the specific value. This conversion of electrical conductivity indicates the optimal pass time. According to this experiment, more than 5 times is enough to distribute CNT uniformly into the matrix.

Figure 3. Electrical conductivities of resin films containing 3wt% CNTs with pass times.

Figure 4 shows fracture surface images of each film processed by different pass times. These SEM images support the results of electrical conductivity. For the samples processed by 1 and 3 pass-time sample (Figure (4a) and (4b)), some resin-rich regions were observed because of poor distribution of CNTs. With the increased pass times, resin-rich regions were reduced resulting in good distribution of CNTs. From the experiments of conductivity and SEM images, we have evaluated the distribution state of CNT quantitatively and found that the optimal pass time for 3-roll mill process is 5.

Figure 4. SEM images of fractured resin film containing 3wt% CNT with pass times (a) 1 pass, (b) 3 pass, (c) 5 pass, (d) 7 pass and (e) 10 pass.

Comparison of distribution methods

As mentioned above, when nano fillers such CNTs, CNFs and nano clays are required to be dispersed into the polymeric matrix effectively, high shear mixing methods are generally needed. In order to evaluate the effect of mixing method on CNTs dispersion, epoxy mixtures for resin films were agitated by a homogenizer. The impeller of the homogenizer typically consists of outer stationary part and inner axis of rotation. The gap between two parts is about 1~2mm. Figure 5 shows SEM micrographs of B-stage resin films prepared by two different methods. In case of the homogenizer, CNTs were agglomerated and resin-rich regions were observed in the composite. On the other hand, the CNT dispersion of B-stage resin films prepared by a 3-roll mill was relatively

uniform. From these results, it is demonstrated that even though rotation speed of the inner axis was very high up to 3000 rpm, the gap distance of mixing tools is more important factor for nano size filler such as CNTs.

Figure 5. SEM micrographs of B-stage resin films: (a) homogenizer (b) 3-roll mill.

Electrical conductivity of hybrid composites

We fabricated micro/nano hybrid composites by laminating the carbon fabrics and B-stage resin film with different contents of CNTs. All the resin films were casted to 300 μm and subsequently cured to B-stage in an oven with hot-air convection. Resultant films were stacked alternately with carbon fabrics and then completely cured in the autoclave. Figure 6 shows the results of in-plane and through-the-thickness electrical conductivities of hybrid carbon fabric composites. The average electrical conductivities in the in-plane direction of composites were improved with the increasing amount of CNT. However, improvement of conductivity was not as much as that of in the through-the-thickness direction. It is attributed to the fact that the in-plane conductivity strongly depends on the property of carbon fibers and volume fraction of carbon fabrics in the composites. Conductivities in the through-the-thickness direction increased by more than 1-order of magnitude with the CNT contents. Moreover, absolute value was also much higher than that of conventional carbon composites. This result indicates that CNT dispersed resin layers between carbon fabrics play an effective roll as a conducting link.

Figure 6. Electrical conductivity of hybrid composites: (a) in-plane and (b) through-the-thickness direction.

Mechanical property of hybrid composites

In order to validate the effect of CNTs on the mechanical property of hybrid composites, a short beam shear test was performed. Figure 7 clearly indicates that all the samples were free of defects. Experimental results in Figure 8 showed a practical tendency to increase in the interlaminar shear strength with the increase of CNT contents. Especially, interlaminar shear strength of the composite with 10 wt% of CNTs exhibited the increase by 14% compared to that of 3wt% of CNTs.

Figure 7. Cross-section images of hybrid composites with different contents of CNTs; (a) 3 wt%, (b) 5wt%, (c) 7wt% and (d) 10 wt%

Figure 8. Interlaminar shear strength of hybrid composites as a fraction of CNTs.

CONCLUSIONS

To improve the mechanical and electrical properties of composite materials, micro/nano hybrid composites were successfully fabricated using CNT-embedded resin films. CNT/epoxy mixtures were also prepared by two different dispersion methods: a homogenizer and a 3-roll mill. Experimental results showed that a 3-roll mill process was more effective than a homogenizer in dispersing CNTs into the polymeric matrix. The optimal pass time of the 3-roll mill was determined quantitatively through the measurement of surface conductivity. Very high amount (10wt%) of CNTs content has been achieved in this study. CNT/epoxy hybrid composites were fabricated with the carbon fabric and CNT embedded resin films by the resin film infusion (RFI) process. The morphology and electrical properties of composites were evaluated and the results confirmed that addition of CNTs has greatly enhanced the mechanical and functional properties of composites.

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